

Rebuttal letter

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This document is a rebuttal letter addressing the two reviews of Giulia Venditti and Davide Brembilla about the first version of the DMP of our research on the Coverage of open citations in DOAJ journals. It was made in the context of the Open Science course by S. Peroni at the University of Bologna 2021-22.

No information about data quality assurance is present for Software data description. But that's also obvious given the state of the research. (Giulia Venditti)

We provided information about data quality assurance stating that we will provide tests along with the software.

Both datasets will be available on GitHub repositories. No other back-up information is present. A suggestion would be to think about multiple media and multiple copies for back-up and to add information on institutional and Github back-up policy. (Giulia Venditti)

We specified also the use of Zenodo as a repository and together with GitHub, both platforms offer back-up policies that we deemed sufficient.

Data management responsibilities have been allocated to named people, also specified by their ORCID. However, at the end of the project, the ensure will be taken by an institutional archive. suggestion would be to clarify data management procedures, considering the variety of data management tasks that may be required for the research. (Giulia Venditti)

Another possible flow is the absence of specific roles in managing the resources and no clear backup is specified. (Davide Brembilla)

We changed the data reuse ensuring to personal archives and public repositories, such as Github and Zenodo. At this stage of research, we currently think it is better not to specify each of the researcher's role, since we are still on a learning process about our research. These informations will be specified later though.

Suggestion to improve the current state, could be the addition of more descriptive information on the contents represented in order to clarify the different type of data needed for the search. In particular, it might be useful to

document collection method, origin, circumstances, processing and analysis of data. (Giulia Venditti)

Dataset could reflect more accurately its contents; this would clear the very different type of content the dataset will have. (Davide Brembilla)

We provided more detailed description of the data in the dataset, as well as some information on the reused datasets (dumps from DOAJ and OpenCitations).

I believe that the description of the software could be clearer by pointing to services that could be used to gather information for the research (e.g. [the DOAJ API](#) or dumps, the [OpenCitations COCI API](#)), as well as Python libraries that could be used in the research. (Davide Brembilla)

We added more detailed information about the software, specifying the reuse of several python libraries: request, Pandas, tarfile and plotly.

it does not seem correct that Zenodo is listed as the open source tool to access the data described. (Davide Brembilla)

We corrected the answer to 3.1.1.20 that we interpreted wrongly in the first version of the DMP.

Thanks to the reports of our colleagues, we produced a new version of the DMP accessible on Zenodo.

References

1. Giulia Venditti. (2022). [Review of: "Coverage of open citations in DOAJ journals v1"](#). Qeios. doi:10.32388/1J0YCK.
2. Davide Brembilla. (2022). [Review of: "Coverage of open citations in DOAJ journals - Data Management Plan"](#). Qeios. doi:10.32388/N2Q3S8.